

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

Project Title	Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities
Project Acronym	BioDT
Project Number	101057437
Type of Project	RIA - Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-TECH-01-01
Starting Date of Project	1 June 2022
Ending Date of Project	31 May 2025
Duration of the Project	36 months
Website	www.biodt.eu

MS23 – Guidelines on Collaboration Principles for RI Nodes

Work Package	WP4 Data and Use Cases
Task	T4.3.1 Capacity and Awareness Building among RI Nodes and European Data Publishers to Deliver the New Data Streams
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Peer Reviewers	N/A
Version	V1.0
Due Date	30/09/2023
Submission Date	29/09/2023

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Funded by
the European Union

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	27/09/2023	Erik Kusch (UiO), Dag Endresen (UiO)	
1.0	29/09/2023	Anna-Liisa Allas (CSC)	Submission-ready version incorporating BioDT PMO final editorial changes

Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
LifeWatch ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research
RI	Research infrastructure

Keywords

Biodiversity, Digital Twin, research infrastructure, biodiversity research data infrastructure, biodiversity informatics

Disclaimer

The BioDT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no 101057437 (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101057437>). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

The BioDT Task 4.3.1 is aimed at capacity and awareness building among research infrastructure (RI) nodes and European data publishers to deliver the new data streams. Progressing from early prototype use cases towards the implementation of digital twins will require capacity building, outreach, and training for the RI nodes. Training events and workshops will enable and inform the change of data management culture to deliver biodiversity data streams while simultaneously progressing towards more advanced data formats. This task is essential to develop capabilities and to enable research communities supported by RI nodes to deliver dynamic data and information originating from different sources as well as stay up to date with evolving analytical and modelling methods. To this end, it is vital that efforts among and across RI nodes are harmonized and collaboration potential is realized. Here, we highlight ongoing work to identify collaboration potential, propose guidelines for improving collaboration and coordination, and expand on future products to facilitate uptake of our proposed principles.

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1. Guidelines on Collaboration Principles for RI Nodes

1.1 Introduction

The digital twin prototypes of BioDT are made achievable through the use and integration of data provided by several research infrastructure initiatives spanning the European biodiversity research landscape. The four core pillars of this research infrastructure backbone of BioDT are the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological research infrastructure (eLTER), Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo), and the e-infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research (LifeWatch ERIC).

Effective collaboration among these European biodiversity research infrastructures (RIs) is essential to support ongoing efforts of the BioDT project, prepare future biodiversity research initiatives in need of integration of comprehensive data and expertise pools, and to continue Europe's legacy as a hotspot for cutting-edge biodiversity research. Consequently, as part of the BioDT project, we (1) have conceptualized a schema by which to assess modes of existing RI (and RI node) collaborations and quantify biodiversity research initiative fragmentations across Europe, (2) provide a set of recommendations for how to augment existing RI (and RI node) collaborations and establish novel interactions among and across RI nodes, and (3) will prepare a shared communication platform for RI node staff to harmonize RI node efforts.

1.2 Assessing Existing RI Collaboration and Fragmentation

To understand the state of collaboration among and across European biodiversity research infrastructures as well as quantify their efficacy and reliability for contemporary biodiversity research, we are currently preparing an initial network analysis. To do so, we express national RI representations as nodes (with RI membership and nationality identifiers) in a network with distinct layers corresponding to collaborations, maintenance, associations, shared projects, shared data or data workflows, and shared citations as tracked via bibliometrics. In doing so, we will be able to aggregate and assess biodiversity RI (node) collaboration saturation and fragmentation at intra- as well as international levels across Europe. Particularly, by linking RI node network topology metrics to national funding and organization structures as well as RI utilization by biodiversity research initiatives, we will be able to identify potential and barriers to effective RI (node) network management and collaboration. In addition, this product need not be static, but rather open to community-sourced updates to node status and network edges through changes to data entries via existing portals like FairSharing with whom we are partnering for this research. Thus, the network analysis we are developing will represent not only an unparalleled investigation of collaboration potential and fragmentation among RI nodes efforts, but also build a platform with which to revisit the European biodiversity RI node network in future iterations.

1.3 Principles for Improving Collaboration Among and Across RIs

Our network analysis will likely reveal complex challenges in fostering collaboration among European biodiversity research infrastructures. We expect these to fall into the following five categories which RI node management must make improvements on to improve collaboration capacities among and across RI nodes:

1. **Lack of awareness.** RI node organizations as well as their staff may not be fully aware of each other's activities and resources. Consequently, resources, data, and services rendered by any one RI node may not be utilized to its full potential by other RI nodes in the European biodiversity RI node network.
2. **Communication barriers.** RIs are complex and highly specialized constructs which have adopted internal communication structures and strategies which fit their respective requirements. However, in doing so communication channels between RI nodes have become fragmented which will likely have created considerable barriers to cross-RI dissemination of achievements, ongoing work, as well as projected undertakings.
3. **Duplication of efforts.** Due to a lack in awareness, existing communication barriers, and persisting need for RI (and RI node) services, the European landscape of biodiversity RI nodes is likely to contain redundant elements. These ultimately drain resources and may lower the usefulness and capacity of the entire RI network nationally and internationally.
4. **Resource constraints.** Limited RI node funding, staffing, and available infrastructure may impede collaboration efforts. These may prove a fundamental barrier for the improvement of the European biodiversity RI network. Thus, identifying these - while also resolving other sources of lowered collaboration success - will be crucial to future-proofing the European biodiversity RI network for the era of integrated analyses.
5. **Varying priorities.** RI node network member organizations operate on different research priorities, objectives, and target demographics. These disparities will be reflected within the network analysis that BioDT will provide.

To address specific collaboration and coordination issues related to these five rubrics, the four RIs involved in BioDT – GBIF, eLTER, DiSSCo, and LifeWatch ERIC – ought to commit to the following principles:

1. **Increasing transparency and information sharing.** Fragmentation of national and European biodiversity research infrastructure initiatives will be best abated and ultimately reversed through higher density of information sharing between RI node members of the same network, across the different organisations as well as disparate organisations within any given nation.
2. **Streamlining and standardizing communication.** Existing communication barriers owing to RI-specific requirements can be diminished or broken down altogether by adopting a standardised approach to communication and dissemination of RI node activities to increase the rate of information flow between RI node organisations.
3. **Coordinating infrastructure efforts.** RI node organisations ought to aim to avoid duplication of efforts and maximise outcome of existing RI and RI node efforts. To this end, it is vital that RI node members communicate plans for RI node efforts among and across RI node organisations to allow for annealing of work plans and sharing of expertise.
4. **Securing and sharing additional resources.** The resources needed for successful biodiversity RI node organisation and governance range from funding availability to labour resources and expertise pools. To secure an increase and share existing resources in these three categories, it is vital that RI node members collaborate closely by (1) jointly seeking funding thus increasing chances of success, (2) intelligently allocate personnel to shared tasks where applicable, and (3) foster a community and space for expertise gathering, building, and sharing to create legacies of individual members.
5. **Aligning research priorities and objectives where possible.** Projects like BioDT are a pivotal gateway to increased collaboration and aligning of research priorities and objectives of RI node organisations.

RI node members should thus seek to continue working on inter-RI-organisational projects to foster a stronger community and build towards a highly robust network of European biodiversity RI initiatives which work towards a common goal through different means and approaches.

We believe that our proposed principles for increased collaboration among the European biodiversity research infrastructure landscape may be enacted through the launch and utilisation of a central communications platform for RI node members.

1.4 Shared Communication Platform: A Way Forward

A shared communication platform for European biodiversity research infrastructures would aid in resolving unresolved collaboration potential and existing action fragmentation as identified through our initial, ongoing network analysis. This platform should serve as a hub for information exchange, coordination, and resource sharing.

Currently, we are trialing such a communication platform hosted through GitHub internally at the University of Oslo (UiO) and are in the process of scaling up its scope and capabilities to function for select GBIF nodes. Following an additional round of feedback from prototype testers, we plan to present the blueprint for a central communication platform for RI nodes towards the end of the BioDT project cycle.

2. Conclusion

Enhancing collaboration among European biodiversity research infrastructures (and their RI nodes) is vital for addressing complex ecological and environmental challenges. An initial network analysis, adoption of collaboration principles, and the establishment of a shared communication platform will facilitate improved coordination and resource utilization among the RI nodes of eLTER, GBIF, DiSSCo, and LifeWatch ERIC. By addressing identified issues and fostering a culture of cooperation, the RI node organizations can work together more effectively to advance biodiversity research and conservation efforts across Europe.

This report resolves the month 16 delivery of BioDT milestone number 23. Another, more formal publication containing findings of the network analysis as well as an introduction to the proposed centralized communications platform will follow in month 28:

MS23 Guidelines on collaboration principles for RI nodes published online (M16 = September 2023)

Means of verification: The guidelines are published.

A strategy on reduced fragmentation of the data actions nationally (RI nodes) and in Europe is to be published on month 28 (M28 = September 2024).